

Determination of Titanium(IV)^{1,2,12a}

The reagent forms a stable 2 : 1 complex with titanium¹², which is moderately soluble in chloroform and in nitrobenzene, less soluble in pyridine and slightly so in benzene, acetone, dioxan, ethanol, methanol and carbon tetrachloride. The complex on crystallisation from nitrobenzene and chloroform mixture melts with decomposition at 283°–284° and is stable in 2N hydrochloric acid solution as well in reaction medium but hydrolyses at and above pH 6.0.

It is utilised as a reagent for the direct gravimetric determination of titanium(IV) and its separation in presence of EDTA from almost all ions except niobium(V) and tantalum(V)¹². Fluoride interferes but can be masked by adding an excess of beryllium solution. Hydrogen peroxide in the absence of EDTA has no effect but when present along with EDTA prevents titanium from reacting with the reagent; this effect of hydrogen peroxide can be avoided by boiling the solution with the addition of sodium hydroxide to remove it and adjusting the pH of the solution to the optimum value before the final precipitation of the element. After precipitation at a pH 2.0–5.0 the reddish orange titanium complex bearing the formula $TiO(C_{13}H_9N_3O_3)_2$ can be weighed after drying at 115–200°C. However, the precipitation also is quantitative at a lower pH 1.0–2.0 but then it needs ignition to oxide before weighing.

From a study of the I.R. spectra of the titanium chelate, the carboxyl group appears to be unreactive. Here the asymmetric stretching frequency of the carboxyl group remains unaffected. It appears at 1680 cm⁻¹. However, the OH band of the reagent is destroyed and a band due to Ti=O appears at 876cm⁻¹. Thus the reagent behaves as a bidentate ligand with a probable composition of the complex as stated.

Determination of copper(II) and palladium(II)^{1,2,13}

These two metal ions precipitate^{1,2} quantitatively from boiling solutions at the pH ranges of 3.0–6.0 and 3.0–5.5, respectively, the precipitates on drying at 115–120° can be weighed as $M(C_{13}H_9N_3O_3)_2 \cdot H_2O$, where M=Cu(II) or Pd(II), and their decomposition temperatures are, respectively, at 250 and 305°. Both the complexes are fairly soluble in pyridine but slightly soluble in acetone, benzene, carbon tetrachloride, chloroform, ethanol and nitrobenzene.

Recently, the pH range for both copper and palladium precipitation has been extended to 2.0–8.0, when the elements can be determined in presence of a large number of ions¹³. The copper complex on drying can be weighed as stated above. While the palladium complex can be weighed as above and also as $Pd(C_{13}H_9N_3O_3)_2 \cdot NH_3$. The methods are claimed to be superior to all other copper and palladium methods. The copper method has been applied successfully to the determination of copper in minerals as chalcopyrites, white metal, brass, tin, bronze, german silver and monel metal.

The reagent behaves as a tridentate ligand in copper and palladium complexes^{1,2}. From IR spectra palladium and copper appear to replace the hydrogen atoms of both the OH and COOH salt forming groups. The asymmetric stretching frequency of the carbonyl group shifts to 1613 and 1650 cm⁻¹ respectively and the OH band of the reagent is completely destroyed.

*Spectrophotometric determination of iron(III) titanium(IV) and vanadium(V) and their separation from each other*¹⁴.

With iron(III) in ammoniacal medium (pH 6.0–10.5), the reagent forms a pink 1 : 2 complex (M : R). On extraction in chloroform it shows an absorption maximum at 500 nm. The increase in the intensity of the color without causing any shift of the absorption maximum is effected by tartaric, citric or oxalic acid. In presence of tartaric acid, the complex obeys Beer's law over the range 0.5–12.0 ppm, the optimum range being 1.0–12.0 ppm. The sensitivity in 0.0112 μg cm⁻² and molar absorptivity is 4970.

The titanium(IV) complex on extraction at pH 1.0–3.5 in chloroform produces a golden yellow extract which has an absorption maximum at 430 nm. At this region the colour system obeys Beer's law in the range 0.25–60 ppm; the optimum range being 0.5–4.0 ppm. The sensitivity is 0.0038 μg cm⁻² and molar absorptivity is 12454. The metal combines with the reagent in the ratio of 1:2.

The chloroform extract at pH 2.0–3.0 of the green vanadium(V) complex obeys Beer's law in the range, 0.5–8.0 ppm with the optimum range from 1.0–6.0 ppm, at 410 nm, the region of maximum absorption. The sensitivity of the color reaction is 0.0062 μgcm⁻² while the molar absorptivity is 8255. The metal combines with the reagent in 1 : 1 ratio.

All the three systems tolerate the presence of a large number of cations and anions.

For the separation of iron(III), titanium(IV) and vanadium(V) from each other, first, the iron(III) complex formed in presence of tartaric acid at pH 9.5 is extracted into chloroform. From the aqueous phase, adjusted to pH 1.0 by hydrochloric acid, the titanium complex is extracted in the same solvent, after the reduction of the vanadate present to tetravalent state and its complexation with thiocyanate. Finally from the residual solution, the vanadium(V) complex is extracted at pH 2.0 into chloroform. The oxidation of vanadium(V) is done by potassium permanganate.

On isolation, the iron(III) and vanadium(V) complexes are found to possess the same 1:2 and 1:1 compositions as in solution. The iron complex of composition $FeH(C_{13}H_9N_3O_3)_2$ is very soluble in pyridine, slightly in alcohol and still less so in acetone, benzene, chloroform and dioxan. But is freely soluble in those solvents on the addition of a drop or two of dilute alkali or ammonia. It decomposes at 212° and is paramagnetic with a moment value of 6.02 BM.

The diamagnetic vanadium complex $V_2O_3 \cdot (C_{13}H_9N_3O_3)_2$ with a decomposition temperature of 163° is very soluble in pyridine, moderately in chloroform, dioxan, ethanol and methanol and slightly so in benzene.

I. R. spectra reveal that in the vanadium complex asymmetric stretching frequency of the carbonyl group shifts to 1625 cm^{-1} . O-H band is destroyed and V=O band appears at 997 cm^{-1} , suggesting the structure

Spectrophotometric Determination of nickel(II), palladium(II) and copper(II) in presence of each other and other ions¹⁵.

In the respective pH ranges of 6.8-8.3, 2.4-3.5 and 2.2-3.8, nickel(II), copper(II) and palladium(II) form in solution, respectively, greenish yellow, yellowish orange and light green 1:1 complexes with the reagent. The systems obey Beer's law in the regions 0.125-2.0, 0.25-5.0 and 0.25-4.0 ppm with the optimum metal concentrations ranging from 0.25-2.0 ppm at 420 nm for nickel(II) and 0.5-4.0 ppm at 410 nm for both palladium(II) and copper(II). The sensitivities of reaction and molar absorptivities are, respectively, 0.0029 $\mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$ and 20284 for nickel, 0.0067 $\mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$ and 16388 for palladium and 0.0044 $\mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$ and 14516 for copper.

In nickel(II) color system, citrate, EDTA, $C_2O_4^{2-}$, Co^{2+} , Pb^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , Fe^{3+} , La^{3+} , Ce^{3+} , Ti^{4+} , Th^{4+} , Zr^{4+} and UO_2^{2+} interfere. In palladium(II) color system, only EDTA, $S_2O_8^{2-}$, SCN^- , Fe^{3+} , Ti^{4+} , Th^{4+} and V^{5+} interfere and EDTA, $C_2O_4^{2-}$, $S_2O_3^{2-}$, Fe^{3+} , Ti^{4+} , Th^{4+} and V^{5+} interfere in the copper(II) system.

For the determination of nickel(II), palladium(II) and copper(II) in presence of each other, two different methods, with the use of complexing agents, are followed. In method I, first to an aliquot oxalic acid is added to suppress the influence of copper(II) and nickel(II) and thus to determine palladium and then to another aliquot sodium thiosulphate is added to prevent the formation of copper and palladium triazene complexes and thus to determine nickel. From the total absorbance, by subtraction, the amount of copper can be obtained. Method II utilises in the same way ammonium thiocyanate for palladium(II) and sodium thiosulphate for both copper(II) and palladium(II). Method I is very accurate but it takes more time for the determination. Method II though not very accurate is easier and less time consuming.

In a preparative study¹⁶, complexes like $CuLX$, $NiLX$, $CoLX$ and NH_4FeL_2 , where $L=C_{13}H_9N_3O_3$ and $X=\text{water}$, ammonia and pyridine, have been isolated and their structures discussed on the basis of their conductivities, X-ray powder diffraction patterns, magnetic susceptibilities, electronic and ir spectra.

1-(2-Carboxy-4-Sulphonatophenyl)-3-hydroxy-3-phenyl-triazene^{17,18,19} as spectrophotometric reagent.

The 4-sulphonato derivative produced by the coupling of 5-sulphoanthranilic acid with phenylhydroxylamine is a yellowish green water soluble compound which forms water soluble complexes. It begins to decompose at 163°C and behaves as a good colorimetric reagent for the determination of various metal ions. Curiously, this reagent does not impart any color with titanium(IV), whereas the earlier reagent^{12,14} is unreactive towards molybdenum(VI).

Iron(III)

With iron(III), it forms at a pH 3.3-4.5 a bluish violet complex having the maximum absorbance at 410 nm where it obeys Beer's law from 0.5-12.0 ppm of iron; the optimum concentration range is 1-12 ppm. The complex in solution bears a metal to reagent ratio of 1:2, with instability constant in the order of 3.48×10^{-8} . The sensitivity of the reaction is $0.0108\text{ }\mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$ of Fe with the molar absorptivity of 5275. For iron system, Pd^{2+} , Cu^{2+} , Mo^{6+} and V^{5+} must be absent as they form colored complexes so also phosphate, fluoride, oxalate, tartrate, citrate, EDTA and thiosulphate which form complexes in acid solution.

Molybdenum(VI)

The yellowish green complex formed at pH 3.0-4.2 shows maximum absorbance at 405 nm. The system follows Beer's law from 1-12 ppm of molybdenum. The colored product with a sensitivity of $0.0207\text{ }\mu\text{g of Mo cm}^{-2}$ and a molar absorptivity of 4812, contains the metal and the reagent in a ratio of 1:2, with instability constant in the order of 2.526×10^{-7} .

For the molybdate system, Pd^{2+} , V^{5+} , Cu^{2+} , Fe^{3+} interfere as do phosphate fluoride, citrate, tartrate, oxalate and EDTA.

Vanadium(V)

The yellow complex obtained at pH 3.0-6.5 shows maximum absorbance at 405 nm and at this wavelength the colored system obeys Beer's law from 0.5-6.0 ppm. The optimum concentration range is 1-6 ppm of vanadium(V). The metal combines with the reagent in a 1:1 ratio with a dissociation constant of the order of 2.11×10^{-4} . The reaction sensitivity is $0.0078\text{ }\mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$ and molar absorptivity is 6623.

In the vanadate system, only oxalate, EDTA, Pd^{2+} , Cu^{2+} , and Fe^{3+} interfere and hence must be absent.

A procedure for the determination of iron(III), molybdenum(VI) and vanadium(V) in presence of each other has been developed with the use of complexing agents e.g. thiosulphate for iron(III) and sodium fluoride for both molybdenum(VI) and iron(III).

Copper(II) and Palladium(II)¹⁸

In the respective pH ranges of 4.8-8.4 and 4.2-8.0, light yellow and golden yellow 1:2 com-

plexes formed by copper and palladium, respectively, obey Beer's law within the optimum metal ion concentration ranges of 0.3–3.0 ppm and 0.4–5.0 at 400 and 410 nm, respectively. The molar absorptivities and sensitivities of reaction are 15333 and 0.0043 $\mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$ for copper and 20222 and 0.0055 $\mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$ for palladium.

In the copper(II) system Ni^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Pd^{2+} , Fe^{3+} , V^{5+} , Mo^{6+} . EDTA, oxalate and thiosulphate interfere. In the palladium(II) system, EDTA, thiosulphate; Cu^{2+} , Fe^{3+} , V^{5+} and Mo^{6+} interfere.

However, in presence of oxalate iron (or oxalic acid, 20 mg) palladium(II) tolerates the presence of Cu^{2+} , Fe^{3+} , V^{5+} and Mo^{6+} upto the limits 80, 100, 50 and 200 ppm, respectively. The reagent is highly selective for palladium.

With the help of masking agents, spectrophotometric determinations of copper(II) and palladium(II) in presence of each other and of the determination of (i) Copper(II), palladium(II) and vanadium(V), (ii) copper(II), Palladium(II) and molybdenum(VI), (iii) Palladium(II), iron(III) and vanadium(V) and (iv) Palladium(II), molybdenum(VI) and vanadium(V) in presence of each other have been achieved.

Nickel(II)¹⁹

The greenish yellow nickel(II) complex stable for 4h, is formed only at pH 7.8–9.2. When 5 ml of the reagent solution (0.05% w/v) is used, Beer's law is obeyed in the range 0.0625–1.5 ppm. of nickel at 400nm with an optimum range of 0.25–1.5 ppm. The reaction sensitivity for the system is 0.00172 $\mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$ and its molar absorptivity is 34524.

Metallochromic indicator for iron(III)¹⁹

The sulphonato derivative finds its use as a good metallochromic indicator for the titration of iron(III) in presence of a number of cations. The color change during the titration with EDTA is from deep blue to green and finally to yellow. The end point is sharp and becomes still sharper when the titration is carried out in presence of cobalt(II) sulphate. At the end point, the color change is then from deep blue to pink. Be^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , Ca^{2+} , Sr^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , Cd^{2+} , Hg^{2+} , Mn^{2+} , Fe^{2+} , Al^{3+} , and Cr^{3+} do not interfere in the direct determination of iron(III). Nickel(II) is tolerated upto 15 mg in 50 ml of the solution.

Oxalate and Fluoride¹⁹

On the addition of oxalate or fluoride, the bluish violet color of the iron(III) complex at pH 3.3–4.5 fades. The fading is directly proportional to the amount of the iron(III) ion withdrawn from the system by the formation of a more stable complex. This is made the basis of a spectrophotometric determination of fluoride or oxalate.

1-(2-Carboxy-5-sulphonatophenyl)-3-hydroxy-3-phenyltriazeno²⁰

The 5-sulphonato compound obtained by coupling 4-sulphoanthranilic acid with phenylhydroxylamine is a light yellow crystalline compound which starts to decompose at 18°C. It is highly soluble in water and is claimed to be the most efficient among the triazenes for the spectrophotometric determination of iron(III) and vanadium(V).

Iron(III)

Iron(III) forms a bluish black complex having λ_{max} at 400 nm. At the pH range of 3.3–10.2, Beer's law is obeyed with optimum range of 1.0–8.0 ppm of the metal ion. The sensitivity of the system is 0.0071 $\mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$ with molar absorptivity of 7890. Iron(III) combines with the reagent in 1:2 ratio with instability constant in the order 10^{-8} . Iron(III) has been determined in presence of Cu^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Mn^{2+} , Pd^{2+} , Ir^{3+} , Ru^{3+} , Pt^{4+} , Rh^{4+} , Mo^{6+} and W^{6+} .

Vanadium(V)

The greenish yellow vanadium(V) complex which shows maximum absorption at 400 nm at pH 2.1–5.9 follows Beer's law from 0.25–5.0 ppm with the optimum range from 0.50–5.0 ppm. The sensitivity of the system is 0.0548 $\mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$ with molar absorptivity of 9180. With the reagent, vanadium(V) forms 1:1 complex whose instability constant is of the order of 10^{-5} . In the vanadate system, only iron(III) and titanium(IV) interfere.

The reagent is also used for the determination of palladium(II), molybdenum(VI), nickel(II), copper(II) and titanium(IV) (Table-1).

It has also been reported^{20a} that due to the substitution of the sulphonic acid group in the 5-position of 1-(*o*-carboxyphenyl)-3-hydroxy-3-phenyltriazeno (A), not only that the derivatives 1-(2-carboxy-4-sulphonatophenyl)-3-hydroxy-3-phenyltriazeno (B) and 1-(2-carboxy-5-sulphonatophenyl)-3-hydroxy-3-phenyltriazeno (C) become water soluble but also that they show characteristic change of properties from the parent compound.

B shows no color reaction with titanium(IV)¹⁷, but A and C both impart^{14,20} colors with it while B is highly sensitive for molybdenum(VI)¹⁷. A and C show poor sensitivity of reaction for this metal²⁰. Again while B is quite efficient as metallochromic indicator¹⁹ and for the indirect spectrophotometric determination of fluoride and oxalate¹⁹, A and C yield poor end points and cannot be used for the anion determinations.

1-(2-carboxy-5-sulphonatophenyl)-3-hydroxy-3-phenyltriazeno also finds application in the determination of metal ions, when present in binary mixtures, with the help of complexing agents. The binary mixtures determined are (i) vanadium(V) and copper(II), (ii) vanadium(V) and palladium(II), (iii) iron(III) and copper(II) and (iv) iron(III) and palladium(II).

water, slightly soluble in chloroform and insoluble in benzene, while the latter complex with magnetic moment $\mu_{eff} = 5.91$ B.M. does not melt or decompose upto 320° and is also insoluble in benzene but soluble in pyridine and slightly so in chloroform and methanol.

The golden yellow titanium(IV) complex, formed at pH 1.0–3.5, on extraction in chloroform obeys Beer's law in the range 0.1–7.7 ppm of titanium at 410nm, the region of maximum absorption; the optimum range being 0.8 to 5.7 and the molar absorptivity is 7.3×10^3 . The titanium chelate on back extraction into concentrated sulphuric acid from its chloroformic solution gives a violet species, the stability of which depends on the amount of water present in the acid. The violet product at its maximum absorption region at 530 nm obeys Beer's law from 2.0 to 23.9 ppm of titanium. The optimum concentration range, however, is 3.4 to 19.2 ppm and the molar extinction coefficient is 2.4×10^3 .

Both the freshly precipitated vanadium (IV & V) complexes are extracted at any pH into chloroform, but not quantitatively. Moreover, from their chloroformic solution, on back extraction with 98% sulphuric acid, violet complexes which are stable for few hours and with absorption maximum at 550–560 nm for vanadium(V) and 550 nm for vanadium(IV) are obtained. They thus appear to form identical species in acid solution. However, two types of vanadium(V) complexes dependent on pH have been isolated. On reaction at pH 5.0 the yellow variety obtained is anionic and is of the formula $H[VO(OH)_2(C_8H_7O_3N_3)]$. The apparently black one, obtained on reaction at pH 1.0, is neutral and is of composition $VO_3(C_8H_5O_3N_3)$. The yellow variety is diamagnetic. It melts at 193° and is soluble in ethanol and water but insoluble in benzene and chloroform. The asymmetric stretch of its carboxyl group and its $V=O$ stretch appear, respectively, at 1617 and 925 cm^{-1} , while its $O-H$ stretch occurs as a doublet at 3077 and 3000 cm^{-1} . The black product of m.p. 214° is slightly paramagnetic and is less soluble in water and chloroform giving, respectively, yellow and violet solutions. In this complex, the $V=O$ stretch is at 995 cm^{-1} and the carboxyl group is free with asymmetric stretching frequency at 1686 cm^{-1} . The green precipitate of composition $VO(C_8H_7O_3N_3)$ with μ_{eff} value of 1.67 B.M., obtained by reaction of vanadyl salt with ethanolic reagent solution does not melt or decompose upto 340° and is insoluble in benzene, chloroform and methanol, but feebly soluble in hot pyridine. Its $V=O$ stretch is at 995 cm^{-1} .

For iron(III) system, interference due to VO_3^- , Co^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Mn^{2+} , Cu^{2+} and Cr^{2+} is removed by tartaric acid at pH 4.0–5.0. However, the interference of F^- is eliminated by an excess of Be^{2+} ion.

With the titanium complex in chloroform, only Fe^{3+} , Cu^{2+} , Cr^{2+} , VO_3^- and EDTA interfere seriously

but the interference of even 200 ppm of Fe^{3+} , Cr^{3+} or Cu^{2+} is eliminated by back extraction from the chloroform layer into 98% H_2SO_4 .

It has been observed^{1,2,12a,21,21a,22,23} that titanium(IV) forms a stable complex with the hydroxytriazenes when a carboxyl group is present in the ortho position of the phenylring and as such titanium(IV) complexes of 3-hydroxy-1,3-diphenyltriazene and 3-hydroxy 1-(*p*-chlorophenyl)-3-phenyltriazene are found to be highly unstable so also when a $COCH_3$ group is introduced in the ortho position or a carboxyl group is in the meta or the para position. However, when a $COOCH_3$ group is present in the ortho position it produces the same stable chelate on the hydrolysis of the ester to the free carboxyl group. This is further established by the reaction of titanium(IV) with the compounds like 1-(*o*-arsenatophenyl)-3-hydroxy-3-phenyltriazene; 1-(*o*-sulphonato phenyl-Na salt)-3-hydroxy-3-phenyltriazene and 1-(*o*-hydroxy methylphenyl)-3-hydroxy-3-phenyltriazenes. Thus for the formation of a stable titanium(IV) chelate the presence of a carboxyl group at the ortho position is highly necessary, even though the chelating agent acts like a bidentate ligand.

For the stable titanium chelate, a hydrogen bridged structure has been proposed on the basis of the infrared spectral studies, which suggest that the hydroxyl hydrogen of the carboxyl group is hydrogen bonded with the titanyl oxygen. This lowers the $\nu_{Ti=O}$ below 600 cm^{-1} and effects the disappearance of ν_{O-H} of the carboxyl group.

Recently the introduction of sulphonic acid group and the said group along with methyl group on the parent compound 3-hydroxy-1,3 diphenyltriazene and their color reaction towards vanadium(V)²⁴ has been studied. The compounds examined are :

- I 3-Hydroxy-1,3-diphenyltriazene
- II 3-Hydroxy-(1-*p*-sulphonatophenyl, sodium salt)-3-phenyltriazene.
- III 3-Hydroxy-(1-*o*-sulphonatophenyl, sodium salt)-3-phenyltriazene.
- IV 3-Hydroxy-(1-*m*-sulphonatophenyl, sodium salt)-3-phenyltriazene.
- V 1-(4-sulphonato, sodium salt-6-methylphenyl)-3-hydroxy-3-phenyltriazene.
- VI 1-(4-sulphonato, sodium salt-5-methylphenyl)-3-hydroxy-3-phenyltriazene.

Table 2 represents the reaction towards vanadium(V)

TABLE 2—SPECTROPHOTOMETRIC DETERMINATION OF VANADIUM(V) WITH 3-HYDROXY-1, 3-DIPHENYLTRIAZENE AND ITS DERIVATIVES

Reagent	Solvent	(a) Color (b) max (nm) (c) Working wavelength (nm)	(a) Beer's law & range (b) Optimal range (ppm)	Sensitivity $\mu\text{g cm}^{-1}$	ϵ	pH range	(a) Composition (b) Dissn. constant
I	Water + ethanol (1+1)	(a) Yellow (b) 410	(a) 0.25-10 (b) 0.5-10	0.0085	5875	3.1-4.2	(a) 1 : 1 (b) 6.0×10^{-5}
II	Water	(a) Yellow green (b) 400 (c) 410	(a) 0.25-10 (b) 0.5-10	0.0085	5875	3.3-4.3	(a) 1 : 1 (b) 6.5×10^{-5}
III	Water	(a) Yellow green (b) 400 (c) 410	—	0.026	—	—	—
IV	Water	(a) Yellow green (b) 400 (c) 410	() 0.25-12 (b) 0.5-10	0.0095	5025	3.6-4.6	(a) 1 : 1 (b) 5.0×10^{-5}
V	Water	(a) Yellow green (b) 410	—	0.05	—	—	—
VI	Water	(a) Yellow green (b) 400 (c) 410	(a) 0.1-8.0 (b) 0.5-8.0	0.0075	6625	3.0-4.4	(a) 1 : 1 (b) 7.5×10^{-5}

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